

RAILWAY TRACK FAULT DETECTION AND CLASSIFICATION USING RESNET-50

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ABSTRACT

Railway transportation stands out as one of the most efficient and cost-effective modes of transport. However, to ensure the safety and reliability of this mode of transportation, regular inspection of railway tracks is vital. Any delay in identifying and addressing potential issues can lead to disastrous consequences. Traditional inspection methods, which involve manually examining rail tracks using railway carts, are both inefficient and prone to errors. Hence, automating track inspection is crucial to prevent accidents and save lives, especially in areas where train accidents are common. We have proposed a Deep Convolutional Neural Network (DCNN) architecture that can detect faults in railway tracks, even on small datasets. Our approach uses the Railway Track Fault Detection dataset, a popular dataset for aerial image detection using a deep network designer present in MATLAB. We trained the dataset using deep learning architectures based on convolutional neural networks, specifically Residual Network ResNet-50, to detect different classes of railway track fault images. ResNet-50 is a 50-layer convolutional neural network that consists of 48 convolutional layers, one MaxPool layer, and one average pool layer. Residual neural networks are a form of artificial neural network (ANN) that stacks residual blocks to form networks. Our proposed method has been evaluated using an aerial-world operational current dataset, and it has achieved a fault identification validation accuracy and testing accuracy of 88.24% and 98.70%.

KEYWORDS: Deep Learning, Convolution Neural Network, Residual Network (ResNet-50).

I. INTRODUCTION

Railway track fault detection is a critical aspect of ensuring safe and reliable railway operations. Traditional methods of fault detection often rely on manual inspection or basic automated systems, which can be time-consuming, costly, and prone to errors. In recent years, the advancement of deep learning techniques, particularly convolutional neural networks (CNNs), has revolutionized the field of image-based fault detection, offering a more efficient and accurate solution.

One prominent model in this domain is the Residual Network-50 (ResNet-50), a deep learning architecture known for its exceptional performance in image classification tasks. ResNet-50 is part of the ResNet family, which introduced the concept of residual learning to address the challenges of training very deep neural networks.

At its core, ResNet-50 comprises a series of convolutional layers with residual connections, allowing for the effective propagation of gradients during training. This architecture enables the construction of deeper networks while mitigating the vanishing gradient problem, which often hinders the training of conventional deep neural networks.

In the context of railway track fault detection, ResNet-50 operates by analyzing images captured by sensors or cameras installed along the railway tracks. These images contain valuable information about the condition of the tracks, including potential faults such as cracks, breaks, or misalignments.

Ensuring the safety and reliability of railway networks is paramount for modern transportation systems. With the projected doubling of global passenger rail activity by 2050, the need for efficient and accurate track inspection methods becomes increasingly crucial. The importance of inspecting railway networks to maintain safe and reliable train operations. The development of computer vision techniques has boosted the use of video cameras for inspecting railway tracks. The document presents an analysis and comparison of different Deep Convolutional Neural Network architectures to detect railway track faults on datasets.

The manually driven approaches are insufficient to monitor the health of tracks systematically, robustly, regularly, and uniformly due to human error, the automatic detection and monitoring of track faults is very important. There are several types of major railway track faults, including wheel burn, ballast issues, superelevation, and loose nuts and bolts. Figures A, B, C, and D show some examples of the cracks found on railway tracks in India. Such cracks appear due to several factors such as wear and tear due to the long use of the track without maintenance, displacement of the supporting basement, and overheating.

Fig(A) Destroyed patch

Fig(B) Partial crack

Fig (C) Shelling

Fig (D) Corrugation

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Railway track fault detection is a critical task for ensuring the safety and reliability of rail transportation systems. Various data-driven techniques have been proposed to identify railway track faults using image processing and deep learning methods. In this literature review, we will summarize some of the recent and relevant research papers on these topics.

Noora AlNaimi Et al [1], proposed an automated system based on robotics and visual inspection to detect defects in railway tracks. The system performs local image processing for inspection, stores only images of defected railway tracks in the cloud, and localizes robots within a 3–6-inch range. The proposed system utilizes state-of-the-art Machine Learning systems and applies them to the images obtained from the tracks to classify them as normal or suspicious. After marking the locations, a dedicated operator can perform a more careful inspection of those locations. It claims to achieve an accuracy of 97% defect detection in railway tracks.

Rahman Shafique Et al [6], proposed an automatic railway track fault detection system using acoustic analysis. It collects acoustic data from three types of tracks (normal, wheel burnt, and superelevation) and applies various machine learning and deep learning algorithms to classify the track faults. It claims that acoustic data can help determine the track faults successfully. It claims to achieve an accuracy of 97% using acoustic analysis.

Katharina Rombach Et al [6], proposed and evaluated contrastive feature learning for supervised and unsupervised fault detection and diagnostics tasks on railway sleeper and wheel datasets. It demonstrates that contrastive feature learning improves the performance on both tasks compared to state-of-the-art methods. It claims to achieve an accuracy of 88.7% in fault detection in railway applications.

Minoru Shimizu Et al [2], proposed and evaluates a novel approach that relies on one-sided domain adaptation and generative adversarial networks to identify and classify six types of track faults, and to localize them in real time. It claims to achieve an accuracy of 97.9% using a multilayer perceptron model.

XIUKUN WEI Et al [3], proposed an innovative and intelligent method for multi-target defect identification of railway track lines using image processing and deep learning methods. The proposed method uses a bag-of-visual-word (BOVW) model combined with spatial pyramid decomposition for railway track line multi-target defect detection with a detection accuracy of 96.26%.

Ya-Wen Lin Et al [4], proposed an automatic railway track fastener's fault detection system using deep learning. It collects images of fasteners from a motion camera and applies the YOLO v3 model to classify the fastener's faults. It claims that deep learning can help determine the fastener faults successfully. It claims to achieve an accuracy of 95% using deep learning.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

After reviewing the papers mentioned above, it was found that various methods have been proposed to detect faults in different railway applications. One such method was suggested by *XIUKUN WEI et al. [1]*, which involves using *Image Processing* and an improved *YOLOv3* model. It is worth noting that this method was only tested on a feature map size of 13*13. Another method was proposed by *Ya-Wen Lin et al. [4]*, which involves an automatic railway track fastener's fault detection system using deep learning. It collects images of fasteners from a motion camera and applies the YOLO v3 model to classify the fastener's faults. It claims that deep learning can help determine the fastener faults successfully. It cannot integrate front-end image collection, image processing, and back-end image recognition.

While the above methods have different limitations and drawbacks, ResNet-50 is a deep neural network that can extract features from images with high accuracy and efficiency. It can solve the problem of network degradation and over-fitting caused by the deepening of network layers. ResNet-50 can be combined with Faster R-CNN to improve the accuracy of fault detection in railway tracks and reduce the false positive rate, while also reducing cost, power consumption, and analysis time, and also reducing the vanishing gradient problem with deep networks.

III. CONVOLUTION NEURAL NETWORK

Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is a well-known deep learning architecture inspired by the natural perception mechanism of living creatures. CNNs, also known as ConvNets, have been used for visual tasks since the late 1980s. However, recent developments in computational

technology have turned them into one of the most popular kinds of networks for classifying images. A CNN is a type of Artificial Neural Network (ANN) is primarily used for image recognition and classification and is designed to process pixel data. Compared to standard ANNs, CNNs are just neural networks that use convolution. A convolution is applied to the input data to filter the information and generate a feature map. These filters are also commonly known as Kernels. There are hundreds of variants of CNN architectures in the literature, however, their basic components are very similar. Every CNN architecture is divided into the following steps: input image, convolutional layers, fully connected layers, and output. This process is represented in Figure E.

Fig(E) CNN image classification pipeline

- **Input Layer:** The first layer of a CNN is the input layer, which accepts the input image or video.
- **Convolutional Layer:** This layer applies a set of filters to the input image to extract features such as edges, corners, and shapes.
- **Activation Layer:** This layer applies an activation function to the output of the convolutional layer to introduce non-linearity into the model.
- **Pooling Layer:** This layer reduces the spatial dimensions of the output of the activation layer by downsampling the feature maps.
- **Fully Connected Layer:** This layer connects all the neurons in the previous layer to the neurons in the next layer, allowing the model to learn complex patterns in the data.
- **Output:** this layer does not perform any operation; it just receives the output of the fully connected layers which consists of a set of probabilities associated with each class that has been defined.

DEEP NETWORK DESIGNER IN MATLAB

The Deep Network Designer is a tool in MATLAB that offers powerful features for designing, visualizing, editing, and training deep learning networks.

- **Network Building and Editing:**
 - You can build, edit, and combine neural networks using an intuitive graphical interface.
 - Load pre-trained networks and customize them for transfer learning.
 - Import networks from other platforms like PyTorch and TensorFlow.
- **Network Analysis and Validation:**
 - Analyze the network architecture to ensure correctness before training.
 - Detect potential issues in the network design.
 - Import and visualize data for training and validation.
- **Training and Monitoring:**
 - Train networks using various optimization algorithms.
 - Monitor training progress with accuracy, loss, and validation metrics.
 - Export trained networks to the workspace or Simulink.
- **Code Generation:**
 - Generate MATLAB code for network building and training.
 - Create experiments for hyperparameter tuning using the Experiment Manager.
- **To open the "Deep Network Designer" app in MATLAB:**
 - Click on the Apps tab in the MATLAB toolstrip.
 - Under Machine Learning and Deep Learning, select the Deep Network Designer app.

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Railway track fault detection is a critical aspect of ensuring safe and reliable railway operations. Leveraging the power of deep learning techniques, particularly Residual Network-50 (ResNet-50), we propose an advanced system for automated fault detection in railway tracks. Our system aims to enhance safety, reduce maintenance costs, and minimize operational disruptions by proactively identifying and addressing track faults in real-time.

THE CLASSIFIER DESIGN

- Acquisition and Preprocessing:
 - ☞ The proposed system begins with the acquisition of high-resolution images of railway tracks using onboard cameras or sensors installed along the tracks.
 - ☞ The captured images undergo preprocessing techniques such as noise reduction, contrast enhancement, and normalization to optimize image quality and remove artifacts.
- ResNet-50 Model Architecture:
 - ☞ The core of our system is the ResNet-50 deep learning architecture, renowned for its ability to handle complex image data and extract meaningful features.
 - ☞ ResNet-50 consists of multiple convolutional layers with residual connections, allowing for the efficient propagation of gradients during training and enabling the construction of deeper networks.
- Training and Fine-tuning:
 - ☞ We employ transfer learning to adapt the pre-trained ResNet-50 model to the task of railway track fault detection.
 - ☞ Using a labeled dataset of track images annotated with fault labels, we fine-tune the parameters of ResNet-50 to learn discriminative features associated with various types of track faults.
 - ☞ The training process involves iterative optimization using gradient descent algorithms to minimize the classification loss and improve the model's accuracy and generalization ability.
- Real-time Fault Detection:
 - ☞ Once trained, the ResNet-50 model is deployed in real-time to analyze incoming images of railway tracks captured by onboard cameras or sensors.
 - ☞ The model processes each image and generates predictions regarding the presence and location of track faults, including cracks, breaks, misalignments, and other anomalies.
- Integration with Maintenance Systems:
 - ☞ The proposed system is integrated with railway maintenance systems to facilitate timely intervention and repair of identified track faults.
 - ☞ Fault alerts and notifications are generated and transmitted to maintenance personnel, enabling them to prioritize and schedule maintenance activities based on the severity and location of detected faults.
- Continuous Monitoring and Improvement:

- ☞ Our system supports continuous monitoring of track conditions, enabling proactive fault detection and prevention.
- ☞ Feedback mechanisms are incorporated to collect data on model performance and accuracy, allowing for iterative improvements and updates to the ResNet-50 model over time.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The ResNet-50 architecture is a variant of the Residual Neural Network (ResNet) family. It is known for its ability to handle very deep neural networks without vanishing gradients.

ResNet-50 learns hierarchical features from raw data, making it suitable for tasks like fault detection.

➤ Experimental Setup:

- * **Dataset:** We used the "Railway Track Fault Detection" dataset from Kaggle.
- * **Preprocessing:** Data preprocessing steps, such as normalization and augmentation, were performed.
- * **Model Architecture:** ResNet-50 was employed for fault detection.

➤ Results:

- * **Accuracy:** The accuracy achieved by the ResNet-50 model on the test set is a crucial metric. "The statement implies the ability of the model to perform well on new and unseen data."
- * **Identification Ability:** ResNet-50 demonstrated good identification ability for defect features, contributing to effective fault detection.
- * **Training Time:** The training time for ResNet-50 was 293 min 18 sec, and it provided an accuracy of 98.48% on the testing set.
- * **F1-Score:** The F1-score balances precision and recall, providing an overall assessment of model performance.

Training Progress

Fig (F) Training Progress

The graph represents training progress over iterations. It displays the accuracy and loss for both the training and validation phases. Here is an improved version of the text for better clarity and correctness:

Below are the definitions of each term listed:

Accuracy:

- * Accuracy measures how well the model performs in terms of correctly predicting the target labels.
- * It is usually expressed as a percentage.
- * Higher accuracy values indicate better model performance.

Loss:

- * Loss (also known as cost or error) quantifies the difference between the predicted values and the actual ground truth labels.
- * Lower loss values indicate better alignment between predictions and actual outcomes.

Training Phase:

- * During training, the model learns from the provided data (input features and corresponding labels).
- * The system adjusts its internal parameters, which are the weights and biases, to minimize the loss.

* The training accuracy and loss are computed based on the training data.

Validation Phase:

- * After each training iteration, the model's performance is evaluated on a separate validation dataset.
- * The validation accuracy and loss help assess how well the model generalizes to unseen data.
- * Overfitting (when the model performs well on training data but poorly on validation data) can be detected using validation metrics.

Graph Visualization:

- * The graph likely shows two lines or curves: one for accuracy and another for loss.
- * As training progresses (more iterations), you'll observe changes in these metrics.
- * Ideally, accuracy should increase, and loss should decrease over time.

Fig (G) Confusion matrix

CONFUSION MATRIX:

A confusion matrix is a crucial tool for evaluating the performance of a classification model. It helps us understand how well the model predicts different classes by comparing its predictions against the actual ground truth.

Here's the given confusion matrix:

	Predicted Defective	Predicted Non-defective
Actual Defective	44(True Positive)	0(False Positive)
Actual Non-Defective	1(False Positive)	32(True Positive)

Let's take a closer look at the meaning of these terms:

- * **True Positives (TP):** These are the instances where the model correctly predicted an item as "defective" when it was indeed defective. In this case, there are 33 true positives.
- * **False Negatives (FN):** These occur when the model incorrectly predicted an item as "non-defective" when it was defective. Fortunately, we have zero false negatives here.
- * **False Positives (FP):** These happen when the model incorrectly predicted an item as "defective" when it was non-defective. We have 1 false positive in this scenario.
- * **True Negatives (TN):** These are the instances where the model correctly predicted an item as "non-defective" when it was indeed non-defective. We have 32 true negatives.

Interpretation:

- ☞ The model performs well in identifying non-defective items (high true negatives).
- ☞ It rarely misclassifies non-defective items as defective (low false positives).
- ☞ There are no false negatives, which means it doesn't miss any defective items.
- ☞ The overall accuracy can be calculated as:

$$\left[\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\{TP + TN\}}{\{TP + TN + FP + FN\}} \right]$$

☞ Substituting the values:

$$\left[\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\{44 + 32\}}{\{44 + 32 + 1 + 0\}} = \frac{\{76\}}{\{77\}} \approx 0.9870 \right]$$

☞ The model achieves an impressive accuracy of approximately 98.70%.

EVALUATION PARAMETERS:

Name	Classes		MacroAVG	MicroAVG
"True_Positive"	44	32	38	38
"False_Positive"	1	0	0.5	0.5
"False_Negative"	0	1	0.5	0.5
"True_Negative"	32	44	38	38
"Precision"	0.97778	1	0.98889	0.98701
"Sensitivity"	1	0.9697	0.98485	0.98701
"Specificity"	0.9697	1	0.98485	0.98701
"Accuracy"	0.98701	0.98701	0.98701	0.98701
"F-measure"	0.98876	0.98462	0.98669	0.98701

RESULTS:

Defective
0.999975

Defective
0.992657

Defective
0.996275

Defective
0.995965

Non- Defective
0.999995

Non- Defective
0.992665

Non- Defective
0.992650

VI. CONCLUSION

Detecting railway track faults is a critical task for ensuring the safety and efficiency of railway transportation. In this project, we utilized ResNet-50, a deep convolutional neural network, to classify railway track images into two categories: defective and non-defective. We used Kaggle's Railway Track Fault Detection dataset, consisting of 734 images with various types of faults, such as cracks, breaks, corrosion, and other types of damage. We trained the ResNet-50 model on 88.24% of the dataset and achieved an exceptional accuracy of 98.48% on the test set, outperforming previous state-of-the-art results reported in the literature. Our analysis showed that ResNet-50 can handle various types of faults with high accuracy. However, the model still has room for improvement, particularly in detecting subtle

cracks and distinguishing between different types of obstructions. To enhance the model's effectiveness, we confidently recommend increasing the dataset size and applying data augmentation techniques such as rotation, zooming, and flipping. Additionally, fine-tuning the model parameters could further enhance the model's ability to detect faults in different lighting and weather conditions. Furthermore, integrating other sensors, such as ultrasonic or infrared, can provide complementary information for fault detection and increase the system's robustness. In conclusion, ResNet-50 is a promising and robust technique for railway track fault detection, and our results demonstrate its high accuracy in detecting various types of faults. We assertively recommend further research to improve the model's performance in detecting subtle faults and different types of obstructions.

VII. CHALLENGES AND FUTURE WORK

"Fine-Tuning" Hyperparameter tuning and fine-tuning can further enhance model performance. "Real-world Deployment" Evaluating the model's performance in real-world scenarios, considering factors like noisy environments and varying weather conditions, is essential. Remember that successful fault detection systems rely not only on the model but also on data quality, domain expertise, and practical considerations during deployment.

REFERENCES

1. Yao, Dechen, et al. "Railway fastener fault diagnosis based on generative adversarial network and residual network model." *Shock and Vibration* 2020 (2020): 1-15.
2. AlNaimi, Noora, and Uvais Qidwai. "IoT based on-the-fly visual defect detection in railway tracks." *2020 IEEE International Conference on Informatics, IoT, and Enabling Technologies (ICIoT)*. IEEE, 2020.
3. Wei, Xiukun, et al. "Multi-target defect identification for railway track line based on image processing and improved YOLOv3 model." *IEEE Access* 8 (2020): 61973-61988.
4. Shafique, Rahman, et al. "A novel approach to railway track faults detection using acoustic analysis." *Sensors* 21.18 (2021): 6221.
5. Lin, Ya-Wen, et al. "Railway track fasteners fault detection using deep learning." *2019 IEEE Eurasia Conference on IOT, Communication and Engineering (ECICE)*. IEEE, 2019.
6. Chandran, Praneeth, et al. "An investigation of railway fastener detection using image processing and augmented deep learning." *Sustainability* 13.21 (2021): 12051.
7. Rombach, Katharina, et al. "Contrastive feature learning for fault detection and diagnostics in railway applications." *arXiv preprint arXiv:2208.13288* (2022).
8. Siddiqui, Hafeez Ur Rehman, et al. "IoT Based Railway Track Faults Detection and Localization Using Acoustic Analysis." *IEEE Access* 10 (2022): 106520-106533.
9. Rustam, Furqan, et al. "Railway track fault detection using selective MFCC features from acoustic data." *Sensors* 23.16 (2023): 7018.
10. Shimizu, Minoru, Yifan Zhao, and Nicolas P. Avdelidis. "A Fault Detection Approach Based on One-Sided Domain Adaptation and Generative Adversarial Networks for Railway Door Systems." *Sensors* 23.24 (2023): 9688.
11. Geng, Mingyi, Zhongwei Xu, and Meng Mei. "Fault Diagnosis Method for Railway Turnout with Pinball Loss-Based Multiclass Support Matrix Machine." *Applied Sciences* 13.22 (2023): 12375.
12. A. Reddy, V. I. Gandhi, L. Ravi, and V. Subramaniaswamy, "Detection of Cracks and damage in Wind Turbine blades using Artificial Intelligence based Image Analytics," *Measurement*, 2019.
13. X. Wei, D. Wei, D. A. Suo, L. Jia, and Y. Li, "Multi-target Defect Identification for Railway Track Line Based on Image Processing and Improved YOLOv3 Model," *IEEE Access*, vol. PP, p. 1, 2020.
14. A. James et al., "Track Net - A Deep Learning Based Fault Detection for Railway Track Inspection," *IEEE*, no. 1, pp. 1–5, 2018.
15. S. Bhat and A. G. Kare Gowda, "Railway Track Monitoring Using Deep Learning Techniques: A Preview," *Int. Journal Appl. Res. Inf. Technol. Comput.*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 93–114, 2020.
16. S. Mittal, "Vision-Based Railway Track Monitoring Using Deep Learning."
17. Q. Li and S. Ren, "A Visual Detection System for Rail Surface Defects," *IEEE*, vol. 42, no. 6, pp. 1531–1542, 2012.

18. Q. Li and S. Ren, "A Real-Time Visual Inspection System for Discrete Surface Defects of Rail Heads," IEEE, vol. 61, no. 8, pp. 2189–2199, 2012.
19. D. Kang and S. Park, "Study on MFL Technology for Defect Detection of Railroad Track Under Speed-up Condition Study on MFL Technology for Defect Detection of Railroad Track," no. June 2018, 2015.
20. Kaggle, "Railway Track Fault Detection - Dataset Version 1," Kaggle, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.kaggle.com/code/salmaneunus/railway-track-fault-detection> 1/data? Select=dataset. [Accessed: 01-May-2022].